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Abstract

This document describes the objectives of the ARCHLAB transnational access program and the activities that have been carried out during the first period (M1-27) of the Iperion HS project.

In particular, the deliverable reports on the archives of the various institutions that are opened for the service, on the initiatives that have been taken to diffuse information on the ARCHLAB opportunities offered to users, and on the various steps that led to the activation of the service consisting of announcement of calls for proposals, projects' selection by peer review, and exploitations of the ARCHLAB infrastructure.

Finally, this deliverable was carried out with some partners of the consortium of WP2 and describes in more detail the projects implemented, the days of access, the objectives of the visits and the results achieved during the visits.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PRP	Peer Review Panel
Nr	Number
TNA	Trans National Access

Introduction

In ARCHLAB platform, access is provided to a set of infrastructures across Europe which possess good amount of knowledge and information of cultural objects as well as archaeological and monumental sites through years of activities devoted to the study, conservation, and safeguard of cultural heritage. The data consist of documentation of the materials, technology, state of conservation, scientific analyses, etc. of the investigated objects. Collections of samples are also available, which are taken from cultural objects, archaeological and monumental sites, and monuments during previous campaigns of study and conservation, and carefully archived after investigations. Scientists, conservators, archaeologists, paleontologists, zoologists and curators in Europe can apply for transnational access to the archives of the infrastructures in a different country. They can carry out comparative or complementary studies related to the scientific research project on which they are working using the physical materials, files and databases held at the host infrastructures. An integral component of access to the infrastructures is the possibility to benefit from the knowledge of experts in the institution specialised in the specific field. The experts contribute via consultation and to the interpretation of data. Access to these data is opening the way for deeper and broader studies than the current ones, leading to more high-quality research. The ARCHLAB platform is an integrated system of 14 distributed facilities located in outstanding European museums and research centres in 9 countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Romania, Spain, Sweden and the UK, see figure 1) :

ARCHLAB_1: Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium/Institut Royal du Patrimoine artistique, Brussels, (KIK-IRPA), BE www.kikirpa.be

ARCHLAB_2: Koninklijk Museum voor Kunst en Geschiedenis/Musée Royal d'Arts et Histoire, Brussels, (KMKGMRH), BE www.kmkg-mrah.be

ARCHLAB_3: Centre de Recherche et des Restauration des Musées de France and Laboratoire de Recherche de Monuments Historiques, Paris, (CNRS#C2RMF-LRMH), FR www.c2rmf.fr and www.lrmh.fr

ARCHLAB_4: Rathgen Forschungslabor Staatliche Museen zu Berlin – Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz, Berlin, (SPK), DE www.smb.museum.de

ARCHLAB_5: Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Firenze, (OPD), IT www.opificiodellapietredure.it

ARCHLAB_6: Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed, Amsterdam, (RCE), NL www.cultureelerfgoed.nl

ARCHLAB_7: University of Groningen (RUG) Groningen Institute of Archaeology (GIA), NL www.lcm.rug.nl

ARCHLAB_8: National Institute of Heritage (NIH), Bucharest, RO <https://patrimoniu.gov.ro>

ARCHLAB_9: Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España (IPCE), Madrid, ES, <http://ipce.mcu.es>

ARCHLAB_10: The Craft Laboratory (CL), Department of Conservation, Faculty of Science, University of Gothenburg (Sweden), www.craftlab.gu.se

ARCHLAB_11: The British Museum, London, (BM) UK, www.britishmuseum.org

ARCHLAB_12: The National Gallery, London, (NG) UK www.nationalgallery.org.uk

ARCHLAB_13: Historic England Laboratory, Fort Cumberland, Portsmouth (HEL-FC) UK

Figure 1: Map of ARCHLAB providers (in light green)

ORGANISATION OF ARCHLAB

1. START OF THE WORK

Specific primary objective pursued by the ARCHLAB providers within the M1-27 reporting period have been the re-activation and widening up of the program, in order to widely diffuse information on the existing and new opportunities offered by the ARCHLAB access among potential users and, by this way, ensuring an effective execution of the service and a regular and appropriate run.

The achievement of these objectives has been possible through the development of the following working steps:

- 1) preparation of the ARCHLAB pages for IPERION HS website (catalogue of services)
- 2) appointment of the Peer Review Panel (PRP)
- 3) opening of the ARCHLAB pages of the IPERION HS website (<http://www.iperionhs.eu>)
- 4) activation of the Welcome Desk to help applicants and to avoid misconceptions
- 5) participation through WP8 to setting up the dashboard and defining uniform access rules and modalities
- 6) participation through WP8 in a harmonization of call for proposals and review processes to contribute to an integrated access approach ARCHLAB-FIXLAB-MOLAB
- 7) preparation and opening of calls for proposals

- 8) eligibility and feasibility of proposals uploaded in the dashboard
- 9) selection of proposals by PRP
- 10) information to applicants and organization of the users' visits.

The open archives of the 14 providers contain documentation on the examination of cultural heritage materials, execution technology, state of conservation, alteration processes of cultural and natural objects, etc., including historical and archaeological information, images, as well as technical and scientific data. In addition to the access to archives and technical data on cultural heritage objects, the platform provides access to collections such as reference samples, zooarchaeological, archaeobotanical, human skeletal, dendrochronological and archaeotechnology collections to support archaeological research held by some of the participating archives, which are useful for providing characteristic and comparative data for researchers. Furthermore, in some cases, additional analyses on these collections as well as on the samples from the users can be carried out, in order to obtain results that can be scientifically compared.

In the IPERION HS ARCHLAB platform, scientists, conservators, archaeologists, paleontologists, zoologists and curators in Europe can apply for transnational access to the archives of the infrastructures in a different country. They can carry out comparative or complementary studies related to the scientific research project on which they are working using the physical materials, files and databases held at the host infrastructures. An integral component of access to the infrastructures is the possibility to benefit from the knowledge of experts in the institution specialised in the specific field. The experts will contribute via consultation and to the interpretation of data. Access to these data opens the way for deeper and broader studies than the current ones, leading to more high-quality research.

General objective of ARCHLAB is to enable to study cultural and natural heritage in a deeper and wider way, opening perspectives for a better circulation of knowledge among researchers in heritage science, permitting an easier achievement of high-level results, avoiding duplications of measurements, and stimulating a deeper integration and wider cooperation among European institutions for the study and conservation of heritage. Furthermore, ARCHLAB enables the alignment of research activities between the user's group and the provider hereby offering opportunities for further networking activities.

2. THE ARCHLAB PEER REVIEW PANEL (PRP)

The scientific panel is in charge of / evaluates the users group proposals on the basis of common peer review criteria, worked out for the 3 platforms through WP8, ranking them and selecting the most appropriate and scientifically sound ones. The 3 PRP members are external experts, recognized for their expertise in the field of heritage science.

The ARCHLAB PRP is the committee in charge to referee the proposals submitted by the users in order to select them on the basis of the scientific merit following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality.

As approved by the Steering Committee the ARCHLAB PRP, is composed by:

Koen Van Balen,
Prof, Departement Civil Engineer, KULeuven, Belgium;

Petria Noble,

Head of Paintings Conservation, Conservation and restoration, Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam, The Netherlands; and,

Gerhard Eggert,

Professor of conservation and restoration of archaeological, ethnological and handicraft objects in the department art conservation restoration, Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste Stuttgart, Germany.

3. PUBLICITY OF ACCESS AND CALLS FOR PROPOSALS

Aim of this work was to guarantee that information about the opportunities offered by ARCHLAB (and relative calls for proposals) reaches the widest audience, in order to ensure a fast establishment of a fluent service run and to increase the opportunities for users.

Access Area web pages

Information on opportunities offered by the ARCHLAB service and announcements of Calls for proposals were distributed through the ARCHLAB Welcome Desk of the Iperion HS website. The ARCHLAB page at the Welcome Desk contains general description of the scope of TNA, mentioning new and existing providers. The pages of the Welcome Desk further contain detailed instructions and guidelines necessary to formulate and submit a proposal, through the dashboard application. Information was also reported on general rules and modalities of Access, as: eligibility of users, modality of presentation of proposals, modality of selection, etc.

All ARCHLAB access providers were involved at all stages in the setting up of the ARCHLAB access pages and the announcement of the four calls enabling the announcement on their own website.

Other communication tools

In addition to the project website, the ARCHLAB Calls for proposals were announced via social media through WP8. Further, a successful webinar was organized in June 2021 dedicated to ARCHLAB. Unfortunately, COVID 19 rules impeded the presentation of ARCHLAB during physical international workshops, conferences and users' meetings, being a crucial opportunity to present the opportunities of ARCHLAB to potential new users.

Since the beginning of the project, four ARCHLAB calls have been announced up to month 27, with the following deadlines:

- call 1: 31 Jan 2021
- call 2: 30 June 2021
- call 3: 30 November 2021
- call 4: 30 April 2022

4. SUPPORT FROM THE ARCHLAB WELCOME DESK

As for the other transnational access platforms of Iperion HS, the Welcome Desk method was applied to ARCHLAB. The Desk consists of an integrated and relevant welcoming service - open for the overall project duration– offered by the ARCHLAB Helpdesk (Ineke Joosten, RCE) and the access provider’s research staff, responding to the user requests regarding technical and scientific information, feasibility of work, logistic aspects, etc. , substantially supporting the users from the proposal preparation up to the exploitation of the visit.

An on-line Application System for the three platforms runs through an automated dashboard and includes a concise presentation of the research project, with a clear indication of the objectives and expected results, the foreseen duration of the access and desired period. A clear indication of the facility or the facilities to which it is requested to accede, must be indicated. At the end of each call, the WP Leader carries out a general check of the scope of ARCHLAB and quality of the proposals, follows up the eligibility and feasibility check, organizes the peer review and adapts the information in the dashboard accordingly.

ARCHLAB ACCESS ACTIVITIES (M1-27)

From the start of the project up to month 27, in total (table 1), 20 projects were received of which 2 were rejected, due to ineligibility issues or too low quality. 16 proposals have been submitted to the Peer Review Panel, related to the first four calls, out of which 13 have been selected corresponding to 19 accesses (some proposals requested access to archives of more than one provider).

Table 1: summary of the selection activities during the reporting period (ARCHLAB); reviewing process by the PRP is through email.

Call (final date)	Number of received proposals	Number of rejected proposals *	Date sending proposals to PRP	Submitted number	Countries	Date final ranking and selection	Selected number
1 st (31 Jan 2021)	7	0	27 Febr 2021	7	IT, PT	27 March 2021	5
2 nd (30 June 2021)	2	0	21 August 2021	2	F, UK, IT	11 Sept 2021	2
3 rd (30 Nov 2021)	6	2	15 Jan 2022	3 ⁽¹⁾	DE, F, NL	12 Febr 2022	2
4 rd (30 April 2022)	5	0	1 June 2022	4 ⁽²⁾	BE, IT, DE	27 June 2022	4
Total number	20	2		16			13

(1): 1 project AORUM was already submitted in call 2 and re-submitted in call 3

(2): ARC20_Oddy-Torium was re-submitted with only a difference in user group composition and not re-submitted to the PRP

Of the 13 selected proposals and 19 access visits, 12 access visits have been realized corresponding to 34 access days. The number of foreseen access visits or projects (19) is below the objective of 44 access visits at M27. This delay can be explained by the covid 19 situation and travel restrictions.

The origin of the selected proposals is quite representative of the European diversity, with a panel of 7 nationalities (Belgium, Germany, Portugal, Italy, The Netherlands, France, United Kingdom).

Error! Reference source not found. gives an overview of the user-projects.

Table 2: overview of user-projects

Name user leader	Nr of users	Project acronym	Objectives	Infrastructure	Nr access (days)	Work carried out
First call						
Francesco Grazi		ARC2_CO MABS		ARCHLAB13_HE		<i>Not realized yet</i>
Vanessah Antunes	1	ARC3_ZAINTIBERIA	The aim of ZAIRIBERIA: Zurbarán's Paintings and its Technical Influence on Iberian Art is to deepen our knowledge provided by 2019 IPERION CH access to IPCE under the theme SINPOS: Spanish Influences in Portuguese Óbidos workshop. In this mission, we could identify technical aspects of Zurbarán painting practices, particularly concerning ground layers.	ARCHLAB9_IPCE	5	Vanessa Antunes is focused on the study of Josefa de Óbidos, the most important female painter in Portugal from the 17th century. Josefa de Óbidos was born in Seville, where her father, Baltazar Gomes Figueira, was working with the Spanish painter Zurbarán. IPCE has deeply studied along the years the majority of Zurbarán paintings most of them from Guadalupe Monastery and the Fine Arts Museum in Seville. The visit was specially orientated to the Zurbarán ground layers, guarded in the Heritage samples IPCE Archive, in order to find similarities and better understand the technology in the Portuguese painter. See Error! Reference source not found. Youtube video: https://youtu.be/jbkOwb2gHGY
Nicoletta Palladino	1	ARC4_ZOZOM	The project aims at the investigation of zinc white. An objective of the archlab visit was to find historical materials for	ARCHLAB_6 (RCE)	2	The archives were checked for the presence of zinc white. Many reports were found and studied. In addition, several paint tubes and reference materials were sampled. Presentation of the project and discussions with RCE scientists on

			analysis and archive sources for mock-ups preparation (e.g., paint recipes, artists' notes).			zinc white. See Error! Reference source not found.
Marco Cardinali	1	ARC5 Imago	IMAGO aims to retrace the roots of Technical Art History, reaching in archives having pioneering work of art historians and scientists in the period 1920-1930 in both the USA and Europe.	ARCHLAB1_KIK-IRPA,	2	During his stay at KIK-IRPA, the user searched in the archives of Paul Coremans to seek the origins of material technical research within the period 1930.
	1			ARCHLAB3_C2RMF	4	Mr Cardinali consulted the archives of the prefiguration of our research laboratory, from the time of Cellierier (1927-1929). These are the first experiments of scientific imaging in France, on paintings of the Louvre (photographs in direct light, UV, X-rays, examination under monochromatic filters). We also provided him with a private archive, that of the restorer Jean-Gabriel Goulinat, who created this laboratory with Cellierier. In addition, he was able to consult the EROS database and analyze X-ray images, in order to make comparisons between analyses from different periods.
	1			ARCHLAB9_IPCE	2	For IPCE access was focused in the identification between Giorgione and Tiziano. For that, Mr. Cardinali was accessing three partial radiographies from the painting "virgin with Child between Saint Antonio de Padua and Saint Roque" s. XVI, realized by IPCE in the late sixties, beginning of the seventies. See Error! Reference source not found.
	1			ARCHLAB12_NG	3	Two particular areas of interest that the user hoped to address through access to the National Gallery archives were the contribution of Alan Burroughs from the Fogg Art Museum, Mass. USA, and the impact of the first international conference on the scientific examination of artworks in Rome in 1930. At the National Gallery the user was able to study a considerable number of x-ray images made by Burroughs of National Gallery paintings during his x-ray campaign in European museums in the late 1920s. The

						user was interested in how Burroughs was using these studies to investigate – among other questions - the distinction between Giorgione and the young Titian; with this in mind he consulted the conservation and scientific dossiers on paintings by these artists, to look at especially the early scientific studies of their materials and technique. He also found much material of interest in the National Gallery archives that related to the history of the use of scientific methods to examine paintings at the National Gallery, mainly from the mid-1940s onwards.
Angela Cerasuolo	1	ARC6_CA MPUS	Capodimonte Museum Proposal of User access for the study of Raphael technique process aims to examine the technical data on the works of Raphael in France to compare them with those of the paintings of Capodimonte.	ARCHLAB3_C2RMF	5	Angela Cerasuolo consulted several dozen files of works by Raphael and his workshop (digital files on the EROS database, paper files, X-rays) (see Error! Reference source not found.).
Second call						
Francesca Gherardi		ARC9_ART DEICS		ARCHLAB6_RCE		<i>Not realized yet</i>
Romain Thomas	3	ARC10_AO RUM	Analysis of gold and its uses as a painting material, end 15th – mid-17th c. Their research project focussed on the use of gold in European paintings from the end of the fifteenth century to the middle of the seventeenth century, meaning in the period after the heyday of gold ground paintings, when the use of gold began to be less common.	ARCHLAB12_NG	3	Before their visit the user group had compiled a long list of National Gallery paintings they wished to study. At the Gallery they were able to study a range of scientific images and data to be able to compile information about the distribution of gold across a painting and also the technique with which it was applied, including details deriving from scientific analysis such as the chemical composition of a mordant used to adhere the gold. The paintings studied were very varied in their geographical origin, including works from France, Spain, the Netherlands, Germany, Italy and Portugal.

Third call						
Simon Steger	1	ARC14_Oddy-Torium	To test conservation materials for their atmospheric corrosivity for the protection of cultural artefacts	ARCHLAB11_BM		<i>Cancelled and reintroduced in call 4</i>
Romain Thomas		ARC15_AORUM	To search for any easel painting, whatever its support (wood, canvas, stone or copper), whatever its technique (tempera, oil...) where the painter has used gold. In addition to gather as many pieces of information as possible about the gilding technique(s) employed by the painter in those paintings.	ARCHLAB5_OPD		<i>Not realized yet</i>
	4			ARCHLAB_6_RCE	3	Consultation of the documentation concerning the analyses, the books with all the cross-sections, and the complete scientific reports of analyses of some artworks. Discuss with the RCE team, present the project in detail. A SEM analysis was done on a selected sample (see Error! Reference source not found.)
	4			ARCHLAB12_NG	2	The user group who visited the National Gallery for arc_10 AORUM requested a second ARCHLAB access visit, as the first had been so fruitful that they felt that the NG documentation archives would be a valuable resource for further study on the same subject. Exceptionally, NG were also able to arrange for close study of some of the paintings themselves by the users in the storage area (AORUM). The users then also took the opportunity to study further scientific files beyond those consulted during the first visit, paying particular attention to certain gilding techniques prevalent in these later paintings, such as shell gold, which seems to have been favoured by certain artists.
Marya Albrecht	2	ARC16_EMPTY	The project entails the conservation and material-technical analysis of <i>The Madonna Enthroned surrounded by angels</i> attributed to Joan Reixach (collection Foundation de	ARCHLAB9_IPCE	3	It is important for the continuation of the conservation treatment to understand how the degraded areas might have looked originally. Research on other paintings by the same artist or contemporaries is necessary, and this is the reason of IPCE access in order to look at technical data present in its archives. See Error! Reference source not found.

			<p>Haar, Utrecht). This painting dates from the mid-15th century and is painted on a wooden panel. The painting consists of two sections separated by carved tracery. The lower part shows Mary seated on a throne with Jesus on her lap. They are surrounded by singing angels, of which two offer vases of lilies to Mary and child. The upper part shows the crucified Christ with the three Mary's on the left. On the right St. John the Evangelist is depicted, together with a small crowd of people on the far right. A walled city is painted in the background. Spanish art of the 15th century is extremely rare in The Netherlands. This painting is one of very few examples in Dutch public collections.</p>			<p>Youtube video: https://youtu.be/j3_E5Gr2it8</p>
Fourth call						
Francisco De Mederos	5	ARC17_ME TOX		ARCHLAB5_OPD	5	<i>Not realized yet</i>
Marie Cristina Tomasetti	2	ARC18_Pd F.exetech		ARCHLAB12_NG	2	<i>Not realized yet</i>
Vince Van Thienen	1	ARC19_TS-CTP-UK		ARCHLAB11_BM	5	<i>Not realized yet</i>
Annalisa Krautheimer	3	ARC20_Oddy-Torium		ARCHLAB11_BM	3	<i>Not realized yet</i>
Hamada Kotb	6	ARC21_MURTECH		ARCHLAB8_NIH	4	<i>Not realized yet</i>

Key Performance Indicators (KPI's)

Following results relate to the KPI's defined in the Grant Agreement.

KPI Demand

% request vs

slots	1st Call	2nd Call	3rd Call	4th Call	AVERAGE
ARCHLAB	1	0,27	0,72	0,45	0,585

SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE

KPI _{E01} . Yearly number of users requests	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4
ARCHLAB	26	5	13	11

KPI _{E02} . Yearly number of granted accesses	Call 1		Call 2		Call 3	
	31/01/2021		30/06/2021		30/11/2021	
	Projects granted	Users	Projects granted	Users	Projects	User Group no.
ARCHLAB	5	9	2	5	3	8

ENHANCING COLLABORATION IN EUROPE

KPI _{E03} . Share of EU users	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4
	31/01/2021	30/06/2021	30/11/2021	29/04/2022
ARCHLAB	1	1	1	1

FACILITATING INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

KPI _{E04} . Share of users from outside the EU	Call 1	Call 2	Call 3	Call 4
	31/01/2021	30/06/2021	30/11/2021	29/04/2022
ARCHLAB	0	0	0	0

ARCHLAB_USER SATISFACTION

KPI_{UserSupport}: 0.8

Target ≥ 0.80 at 18 months

Practical information on how to apply as well as the scientific and technical advice available from the User helpdesk

KPI_{feedback} : 0.85

Target ≥ 0.80 at 12 months after first access

Overall fulfillment of expectations.

CONCLUSION

These results show a clear decline in access requests in call 2, followed by a rather continuous increase in later calls. Users are entirely EU users who are satisfied about the support offered and the fulfillment of expectations of the offered accesses.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

A draft document was set up “Overview of consulted and prepared data” that guides ARCHLAB providers and users through data management requirements, as outlined in the Iperion HS DATA MANAGEMENT plan worked out in 6.3. The document aims to provide an overview of different types of consulted (meta)data and their accessibility (i. consulted datasets (background data or any tangible or intangible input that exists before the visit (for example: internal (paper)dossier, its number, PID or hyperlink), short description of the data type (for example radiographic analyses, RAMAN data, ...) to which meta-data can be added according to existing metadata scheme, licences and IPR, ...; ii) required background data (the minimum to enable a collaboration, for example a photo) and iii) generated results. The document is kept as simple as possible and consists of text boxes to fit the diversity of data as found in archives to enable an easy implementation and is to be deposited (along with the data) in Zenodo.

CONCLUSION

20 projects were received during the first 4 calls, of which 2 were rejected, due to ineligibility issues or too low quality. 16 proposals have been submitted to the Peer Review Panel, out of which 13 have been selected corresponding to 19 accesses (some proposals requested access to archives of more than one provider).

The 19 foreseen projects is below the objective of 44 access visits at M27. This delay can be explained by the covid 19 situation and travel restrictions, as well as the shortened call-periods (5 months instead of 6 months).

From the start of the project up to month 27, 12 visits took place corresponding to 34 access days. From the received feedback, users are satisfied about the support offered and the fulfillment of expectations of the offered accesses.

A document was setup that enables the management of the consulted and, eventually, generated data to be implemented for the accesses that took place.

Figure 2: Ms Autunes evaluating ground laters of Zurbaran at IPCE

Figure 3: ARC4_ZOOM, Claudia Palladino during her visit at RCE

Figure 4: Mr Cardinali evaluating radiographs at IPCE

Figure 5: Ms Marya Albrecht (in the middle) and Gert Van Gerven (bottom left)

Figure 6: Angela Cerasuolo consulting files of works by Raphael at C2RMF

Figure 7: ARC15_AORUM, User group during the visit at RCE

ANNEX
Table: Researcher Information

RESEARCHER				EMPLOYING ORGANIZATION/ HOME INSTITUTION			OTHER INFORMATION	
First Name	Last Name	Nationality	Gender	Name	Legal status ¹	country	User project acronym	Activity domain ²
Lafarga	Manuel	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES	MRVWCXR	Humanities Information and Communication technologies
Camarero Manzanero	Jorge	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES		
Sanz	Penelope	ES	Female					
Chafer Bixquert	Teresa	ES	Female	Universitat Politecnica de Valencia (UPV)	UNI	ES		
Roig Picazo	Pilar	ES	Female	Universitat Politecnica de Valencia (UPV)	UNI	ES		
Fenlon	Iain	GB	Male	University of Cambridge	UNI	GB		
Asensi Seva	Vicente	ES	Male	Conservatorio Superior de Música de Alicante	RES	ES		
Grazzi	Francesco	IT	Male	CNR - IFAC	RES	IT	COMABS	Engineering and Technology Humanities Material Science Physics
Cantini	Francesco	IT	Male	Università di Firenze - Dipartimento di Fisica	UNI	IT		
Antunes	Vanessa	PT	Female	Instituto de História da Arte da Faculdade de Letras da Universidade de Lisboa (ARTIS-IHA)	UNI	PT	ZAINTIBERIA	Humanities Material Science
Palladino	Nicoletta	IT	Female	C2RMF	RES	FR	ZOoMM	Chemistry Material Science Physics
Salvant	Johanna	FR	Female	C2RMF	RES	FR		

Cardinali	Marco	IT	Male	Università della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli"	UNI	IT	IMAGO	Humanities
Cerasuolo	Angela	IT	Female	Museo e Real Bosco di Capodimonte	RES	IT	CAMPUS	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics
Zeza	Andrea	IT	Male	Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli"	UNI	IT		
Damiani	Suzana	HR	Female	University of Zagreb, Academy of Fine Arts	UNI	HR	DiODuCat - A	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Zeman	Maja	HR	Female	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences	UNI	HR		
Martinović	Ivan Vanja	HR	Male	University of Zagreb, Academy of Fine Arts	UNI	HR		
Gherardi	Francesca	IT	Female	Historic England	RES	GB	ARTDEICS	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Sarah	Paynter	GB	Female	Historic England	RES	GB		
THOMAS	Romain	FR	Male	Paris Nanterre University	UNI	FR	AORUM	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Physics Social sciences
LE HÔ	Anne-Solenn	FR	Female	Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France (C2RMF)	RES	FR		
DUBOST	Marie	FR	Female	Atelier de la feuille d'or	SME	FR		
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Świtezak	Paula Karina	PL	Female	Nicolaus Copernicus University	UNI	PL	MET_HER	Chemistry Humanities Material Science
Tomassetti	Maria Cristina	IT	Female	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT	PDF.exe.tech.	Humanities
Picchiarelli	Veruska	IT	Female	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT		
Costantini	Daniele	IT	Male	Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria	OTH	IT		
Steger	Simon	AT	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE	Oddy-torium	Chemistry Earth Sciences & Environment Material Science
HRISTOVA	Valentina	BG	Female	Université Paris Nanterre	UNI	FR	AORUM	Chemistry Humanities Information and Communication

								technologies Material Science Physics Social sciences
Albrecht	Marya	NL	Female	Atelier Albrecht Schilderijenrestauratie	SME	NL	EMPTY	Humanities
Daugherty	Melissa	NL	Female	Restauratieatelier Daugherty	SME	NL		
Van Gerven	Gert	NL	Male	Studio Van Gerven	SME	NL		
Mederos-Henry	Francisco	BE	Male	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE	MetOx-IT	Chemistry Humanities
Sanyova	Jana	SK	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE		
Collignon	Amandine	BE	Female	Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage	RES	BE		
Quintero Balbás	Diego IVán	MX	Male	National Institute of Optics	RES	IT		
Van Thienen	Vince	BE	Male	Ghent University	UNI	BE	TS-CTP-UK	Earth Sciences & Environment Humanities
Krautheimer	Anna Lisa	DE	Female	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE	Oddy-torium	Chemistry Material Science
Krekel	Christoph	DE	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE		
Eggert	Gerhard	DE	Male	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	UNI	DE		
Kotb	Hamada	EG	Male	The University of Bologna	UNI	IT	MURTECH	Chemistry Humanities Material Science Social sciences

1 UNI- University and other higher education organizations
 RES- Public research organization (including international and private research organizations controlled by a public authority)
 SME- Small or Medium Enterprises
 PRV- Other Industrial and/or profit Private organization
 OTH- Other organization not fitting in one of the above category

- 2 Chemistry
 Earth sciences and Environment
 Energy
 Engineering and Technology
 Humanities
 Information and Communication Technologies
 Life sciences and Biotech
 Material sciences
 Mathematics
 Physics